

Towards a Safe and Secure Internet of Things Critical Infrastructure

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Abstract—The IoT also have many applications in commercial sectors, such as environmental monitoring, infrastructure management, smart buildings, and smart cities. This work has proposed and studied the development of novel and efficient security techniques that can protect IoT devices and enable secure communications over the Internet. Specifically, we have proposed (1) hardware based schemes for establishment of root of trust; (2) the design of a reliable and secure key generator and management system using SoC FPGA; (3) development of novel hardware-based secure authentication schemes for IoT devices; and (4) design of light-weight secure communication protocols for IoT devices.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, hardware-based security, embedded systems, SoC, FPGA, secure communications

Fig 1: IoT fields of application

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of physical objects, such as computing and sensing devices, vehicles, buildings or other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors [3], and network connectivity. IoT enables these objects to collect and exchange data of interest. The IoT devices allow physical objects to be sensed and controlled remotely across a network infrastructure, resulting in improved operation, efficiency, and economic benefits. Whether called the Internet of Everything (IoE), machine-to-machine, or ubiquitous or embedded or ambient computing, the IoT is fundamentally about connecting disparate objects into larger networks. The IoT is transforming many key industries. Based on a recent estimation [1][2], the number of IoT devices deployed worldwide will grow from 5 billion in 2015 to 24 billion in 2020, forming a global market of \$13 trillion dollars [10][11]. IoT has a lot of applications (Fig.1) such as smart cars, intelligent transportation systems and other critical infrastructure (e.g., power grid, SCADA), smart cities, oil and gas, industrial control systems (ICS), manufacturing, healthcare, battlefield and environment surveillance, reconnaissance, acquisition and processing of commercial and/or military intelligence, logistics, etc.

Some key challenges faced by the IoT infrastructure are safety, security and privacy [23][7][8][18][17][12]. With information so central to all activities of today's society, safe and secure technologies and tools that improve data collection, communication, routing, or processing of information in the realm of IoTs are in critical demand. However, due to the lack of effective and efficient security protection of IoT devices as well as the communications between the IoT devices and the Internet, the applications of IoTs have been hampered.

In this paper, we present challenges and some effective, efficient security techniques for protecting industrial IoTs and IoT critical infrastructures.

II. SECURITY CHALLENGES IN IOTS

Today, the communication infrastructure faces many threats whether it is a home Wi-Fi network or an organization's network. Networked devices and systems, be it a smart TV, or an IP camera, or other devices, are all at risk. This constant risk is no different for industrial IoTs and their supporting infrastructure. Due to the open architecture of many IoTs, this makes it much more difficult to secure these devices, bringing about many more security challenges. Numerous properties of IoTs have led to security and privacy issues which are exacerbated by mobility, wireless communication, embedded use, diversity, and scale. These characteristics make IoT unique in its security needs and raise many new challenges in information security.

Fig 2: Layered IoT architecture

Fig 2 illustrates the layered architecture of networked IoTs. We examine various aspects of IoT security challenges that may arise in each layer briefly.

A. Security Issues in Perception Layer

This is the lowest level of IoT construction. Perception layer is the source of access to information throughout the IoT. This layer deals with IoT sensors and actuators. Sensors sense the physical phenomenon occurring around them. Actuators on the other hand perform a certain action on the physical environment, based on the sensed data. There are various kind of sensors for sensing different kinds of phenomena like the ultrasonic sensors, camera sensors, smoke detection sensors, temperature and humidity sensors.

The security issues in the perception layer include physical security of sensing devices and security of information collection. It is challenging for IoTs to provide a security protection system and therefore they are vulnerable to attacks due to diversity, limited energy, simple and weak protective capability of sensing node which affects the security of wireless sensor networks, RFID and M2M terminals. The RFID has security problems such as information leakage, replay attacks, information tracking, tampering, cloning attacks and man-in-the-middle attacks. The security problems faced in perception layer includes gateway capture, physical capture, unfair attacks, congestion attack, DoS attacks, node replication attack and forward attack.

Node Capture Attack: Resource constrained nodes such as sensors and actuators often lack physical security. The attackers may try to capture or replace the node in the IoT system with a malicious node. The new node may appear to be a part of the system but is controlled by the attacker. This may lead to compromising the security of the complete IoT system and application.

Malicious Code Injection Attack: The attack involves the attacker injecting some malicious code in the memory of the node. Generally, the firmware or software of IoT nodes are upgraded on the air, and this gives a gateway to the attackers to inject malicious code. They may force the nodes to perform some unintended functions or may even try to access or control the entire IoT system.

False Data Injection Attack: Once a node is captured, the attacker may use it to inject erroneous data onto the IoT system.

This may lead to false results and may result in malfunctioning of the IoT application.

Side-Channel Attack: This type of attacks may lead to leaking of sensitive data. The micro architectures of processors, electromagnetic emanation and their power consumption may reveal sensitive information to adversaries. Side channel attacks may be based on power consumption, laser-based attacks, timing attacks or electromagnetic attacks.

Eavesdropping and Interference: IoT applications often consist of various nodes deployed in open environments which result in exposure to eavesdropping. They may capture data during transmission and authentication phases.

Sleep Deprivation Attack: These attacks drain the battery of the IoT edge devices. This may lead to denial of service from the nodes in the IoT application.

Bootling Attacks: The devices become vulnerable during the boot process as the security processes are not enabled at that point.

B. Security Issues in Network Layer

IoT faces risks in the network like illegal access, breach of confidentiality, data eavesdropping, integrity, DoS attacks, destruction, virus attack, man-in-the-middle attack and so on. IoT sensing of many devices may lead to a variety of formats of the data collected, and the amount of data can be massive, multi-source and heterogeneous. These characteristics may also cause network security issues such as data transfer needs of large number of nodes may lead to network congestion, resulting in DoS attacks. One of the functions of the network layer is routing. Attackers may also target this critical service of the network layer. Some of the security threats encountered in this layer are:

Phishing Site Attack: This refers to the attack where several IoT devices can be targeted by a minimal effort put by the attacker. There is a possibility of encountering phishing sites in the course of users visiting web pages on the Internet. Once the user's account is compromised. The whole IoT environment being used by the user may become vulnerable to cyber-attacks.

Access Attack: In this type of attack an unauthorized person or an adversary gains access to the IoT network. They may stay in the network for a long time undetected and can steal valuable information. This type of attack is, to some degree, akin to advanced persistent threat (APT).

DDoS/DoS Attack: In this kind of attack, the attacker floods the target with many unwanted requests. This incapacitates the target device, thereby disrupting its normal services to the user.

Data Transit Attack: IoT applications deal with a lot of data storage and exchange. The data that is in transit or is moving from one location to another is more vulnerable to cyber-attacks. Different technologies are used in such data movements and therefore IoT applications are susceptible to data breaches in the process.

Routing Attack: The malicious nodes try to redirect the routing paths during data transit. Sinkhole attacks (Fig. 3) are a specific kind of routing attack in which the attacker advertises an artificial shortest routing path and attracts nodes to route traffic through it.

Fig 3: Sinkhole Attack

Acknowledgement Flooding Attack: When routing algorithms are used, acknowledgements are required at times in various networks. In acknowledgements flooding attack, a malicious node may spoof the acknowledgements, providing false information to the destined neighboring nodes or the source node.

C. Security Issues in Middleware Layer

The role of the middleware in IoT is to create an abstraction between the network layer and the application layer. It also provides powerful computing and storage capabilities. The middleware contains the APIs to fulfill the demands of the application layer. Database security and cloud security are the main security challenges of the middleware layer.

Man-in-the-Middle Attack: The MQTT protocols uses publish-subscribe model of communication. The MQTT broker acts as the proxy. If the attacker can get the control of broker and become a man-in-the-middle, then he/she can get complete control of the communication.

SQL Injection Attack: The attacker can embed malicious SQL statements in a program and can obtain private data of any user and can even alter records in the database.

Signature Wrapping Attack: In the web services used in the middleware, XML signatures are used. In a signature wrapping attack, the attacker breaks the signature algorithm and can execute operations or modify eavesdropped messages by exploiting vulnerabilities in the SOAP.

Cloud Malware Injection: In cloud malware injection attack, the attacker pretends to be a valid service by trying to create a virtual machine instance and tries to obtain access to service requests of the victim's service and capture sensitive data

Flooding Attack: Similar to the DoS attack in the cloud, this type of attacks affects the quality of service. To deplete cloud resources, the attackers continuously send multiple requests to a service. They increase the load on the cloud servers to the point of rendering the service not useable.

D. Security Issues in Gateways

Gateways is a broad layer that has an important role in connecting multiple devices, people, things and cloud devices. Gateways help in providing hardware and software solutions to IoT devices. Gateways are used for encrypting and decrypting

IoT data and translating protocols for communication between different layers. The security issues encountered in this layer are:

Secure On-Boarding: When a new device is added in an IoT system, it is necessary to protect encryption keys. Gateways act as an intermediary between new devices by managing services and all keys that pass through the gateways which can be captured by eavesdropping or man-in-the-middle attacks

Extra Interfaces: Minimizing the attack surface is an important strategy in IoT. Some services which cause backdoor authentication or information breach should be restricted. However, attackers may exploit the availability of extra interfaces.

End-to-end Encryption: The application should not let anyone other than the designated recipient to decrypt and encrypt messages. However, gateways often break the semantics of end-to-end encryption, therefore presenting as a vulnerability.

E. Security Issues in Application Layer

Application of IoT is the result of close integration between communication technology, computing technology, cloud storage, and operating systems. IoT application have found its way in almost all fields. Depending on application, this layer also provides software to carry out the translation of data, or helps in collecting information by sending queries. The security issues in the application layer include eavesdropping and tampering among others. A path-based DoS attack may be initiated in the application layer by stimulating the sensor nodes to create a huge traffic in the route towards the base station/gateway. Numerous attacks are possible at this layer.

Data Thefts: IoT applications deal with a lot of critical and private data. The data in transit is even more vulnerable to attacks than data at rest, and in IoT applications, there is a lot of data movement. The users will be reluctant to register their private data on IoT applications if these applications are vulnerable to data theft attacks. Data encryption, data isolation, user and network authentication, privacy management, etc. are some of the techniques and protocols being used to secure IoT applications against data thefts.

Access Control Attack: Access control is authorization mechanism that allows only legitimate users or processes to access the data or accounts. Access control attack is a critical attack in IoT applications because once the access is compromised, then the entire IoT application becomes vulnerable to all sorts of attacks.

Service Interruption Attack: This type of attacks is also referred to as illegal interruption attacks or DDoS attacks in existing literature. There have been various instances of such attacks on IoT applications. Such attacks deprive legitimate users from using the services of IoT applications by artificially making the servers or network too busy to respond.

Malicious Code Injection Attack: Attackers generally go for the easiest or simplest method they can use to break into a system or network. If the system is vulnerable to malicious scripts due to insufficient code checks, then that would be the first entry point that an attacker would choose. Generally,

attackers use XSS (cross-site scripting) to inject some malicious scripts into an otherwise trusted website. A successful XSS attack can result in the hijacking of an IoT account and can paralyze the IoT system.

Sniffing Attack: The attackers may use sniffer applications to monitor the network traffic in IoT applications. This may allow the attacker to gain access to confidential user data if there are not enough security countermeasures implemented to prevent it.

Reprogram Attack: If the programming process is not protected, then the attackers can try to reprogram the IoT devices remotely. This may lead to the hijacking of the IoT network/system.

III. PROPOSED TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS

In this section, we present and discuss our solutions to some of the security challenges IoTs face currently.

A. IoT Security by Design

So far the security of IoT systems has been approached in an ad-hoc fashion where security measures (i.e., “patches”) are put in place when an attack or a vulnerability is discovered. Considering that the IoTs will work at a scale on the order of billions of devices and connecting critical infrastructure (Fig. 4), we advocate that security must be deeply embedded in every stage of the production cycle, from product design to development and deployment. The concept of security-by-design should be a main driving force in IoT security research and development.

Security-by-design is an approach that has been traditionally applied to software and hardware development [21]. It seeks to make systems as free of vulnerabilities and impervious to attacks as possible before the system is deployed. Achieving security-by-design in IoTs is significantly challenging, given the scale, complexity, and heterogeneity of the IoT devices and the diversity of networking systems. Our solution is to provide security mechanisms on a wholistic and end-to-end basis, starting from establishing the root of trust of IoT devices, secure boot and execution of verified applications, to device authentication [19][13][22] and secure lightweight communication among various entities and components of a complex and heterogenous IoT ecosystem.

The first step in securing an IoT device is to ensure that it can start up under the following conditions: (1) It operates as expected; (2) All the firmware needed to run the system is intact; and (3) It has not been tampered with in any way. This requires secure boot and using validated firmware that has been digitally signed and verified. Ultimately, a chain of trust that is based on the root of trust needs to be established. The root of trust is ideally based on a hardware-validated boot process to ensure the system can only be started using code from an immutable source. Since the anchor for the boot process is in hardware, it cannot be updated or modified in any way. When this foundation is combined with the cryptographically secured boot process, there are no easily accessible gaps for hackers to exploit.

The important aspect for a root of trust (Fig. 5) is to ensure that the initial code is what the manufacturer intended, before execution. Upon starting, the root of trust derives its internal keys from supplied device identity inputs and executes self-tests and code validation for itself. If these tests pass, the IoT system can move on to validate the first piece of code in the chain of trust (Fig. 6).

Fig 4: Components of IoT ecosystem of various applications

Root of Trust

Establishing SW / HW Trust

1. Hardware to BootROM
2. BootROM to Operating System
3. Operating System to Application

Fig 5: Root of trust

B. Securing IoT Devices via Novel Hardware Design

To achieve effective and efficient security of IoT devices, we design and develop a System-on-Chip (SoC) based approach for IoT device protection where SoC integrates flexible software and high-performance hardware and implements sophisticated security functions in real-time with both static and dynamic update mechanisms.

Any secure and reliable network should have both information security and infrastructure security. Information security aims at data protection via authentication and encryption whereas infrastructure security focuses on protecting network resources and communication where information is shared. All relevant devices connected to the network can be considered as infrastructure components, such as IoT devices, mobile devices, end-hosts, Domain Name Server (DNS), routers, switches, and so on. They are highly attractive targets for attacks. However, for the IoT infrastructure to be secure, these components and the communications among them need to be secured.

and implementing hardware-based network security to maintain the flexibility and keep the design up to date.

Fig 7: Trend of security implementation

Fig 6: Code signing and verification

Due to the large scale of and the limited host processor computation power in many IoT systems, effective security provisioning is shifting from pure software-based security implementation to hardware-based security implementation in terms of efficiency and effectiveness for critical infrastructures, illustrated in Fig. 7. Specifically, pure software-based applications are not adequate in industrial IoT and critical infrastructure with higher data rates, for example, Bro and WebSTAT cannot handle data rates higher than 100M bits per second (Mbps). Moreover, increased network bandwidth can make all off-the-shelf processors overburdened and hard to maintain high throughput. Using dedicated hardware assist (e.g., SoC, FPGA) can relieve the burden on processors. Meanwhile, the SoC can take over the work of infrastructure components to preserve and protect critical components and minimize the negative impacts on these components. IoT devices must be able to verify the code they run, establish their trustworthiness to other devices, and securely connect to other devices on or off the Internet.

In terms of computation capability, a hardware-based solution can efficiently support parallel executions whereas software-based solutions are often less efficient. Efficient parallel data computation and multi-stage processing are features of SoC-based implementation of infrastructure security that cannot be effectively achieved by pure software. Moreover, re-configurability is another essential requirement for designing

The main challenges of designing such a proposed SoC-based security system are to defend against threats and attacks to an SoC FPGA design. These threats and attacks include: (1) bitstream decoding where the attackers can recover a bitstream or original netlist by decoding the bitstreams; (2) spoofing where all or parts of an FPGA bitstreams or microprocessor program is replaced or modified; and (3) Trojan Horse where the system is accessed by hackers who insert their own logic functions into the design to access data stored in FPGA, obtain insight of the overall design, or hijack the system. Therefore, in this paper, we propose to (1) encrypt FPGA bitstreams to protect it from bitstream decoding; (2) ensure the FPGA operates correctly as intended via authentication to avoid spoofing and Trojan Horse attacks; and (3) migrate operating system (OS) schedulers and other critical OS functions into the FPGA logic, which would reduce the attack surface and increase the attackers' workload in addition to preventing some attacks [20][14].

C. Designing a Robust and Secure Key Generator and Management System using SoC

SSL/TLS/DTLS and code signing have proven to be critical to the security of critical industrial IoT devices. Roots of trust are the foundation of both code signing and SSL/TLS/DTLS encryption and authentication. With roots of trust embedded in the user's device, the device can use a root to verify the authenticity of certificates signed by or chained to that root. Mutual authentication is a cornerstone of IoT security. Such authentication is an important step in bootstrapping encrypted communications. Strong mutual authentication is critical for end users connecting to IoT services, for devices communicating to central services, and for peer-to-peer communication between devices.

We will design and demonstrate a reliable and secure key generator and management system using SoC FPGA. The design is built on the physically unclonable function (PUF) of an IoT device to support confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) (Fig. 8). This PUF key will be the master key used to generate different secure keys for different security functions such as encryption and authentication. The keys can also be used to encrypt bitstream and calculate keyed-hash

message authentication code (HMAC) for bitstream. Bitstream encryption can be used to avoid an adversary to reverse engineer the configuration bitstream or upload a bitstream without knowing the key. Bitstream authentication can detect any bitstream tampering, including a flip of a single bit. Ultimately, the root of trust and associated security mechanisms offer the unprecedented protection of IoT devices.

Fig 8: Hardware based key generation

D. Novel Hardware-based Secure Authentication Schemes for IoT Devices

Before an IoT device communicates with a server, authentication is needed to ensure that only authorized devices are allowed. A number of challenges for designing secure authentication schemes for IoT devices exist, for example: (1) *constrained resource*. A lot of IoT devices are battery driven devices that are expected to run for years. Many IoT devices have very limited computational resources. (2) *high-security requirement*. The devices may have high-security requirement because they may be deployed in critical infrastructures or systems, such as power grids.

IoT devices security should be based on light-weighted cryptographic primitives. We propose a 3-tier security model where the authentication server is utilized to authorize a programmer (e.g., a RFID reader) and grant permissions to the programmer/reader for accessing the IoT devices. We propose utilizing hardware-based security - the Physically Obfuscated Keys (POKs) enabled IC card to strengthen the system security and provide a secure solution for IoT device access. Additionally, we propose a recovery approach to enable re-key of an IoT device if the IC card is lost or stolen.

Physically Obfuscated Keys (POKs) [15], also known as Physically Random Functions, are a special means to store secret keys. It is proposed to satisfy the central assumption in cryptographic protocol: participants are able to protect and differentiate themselves with adversaries by the secret key that is only accessible by themselves. Encryption and digital signatures are both built on the assumption that participants have the capability of keeping their secret key safe. However, keeping a secret key is extremely difficult to accomplish, especially when the devices are physically accessible by adversaries and many efficient methods to extract keys from Flash or EPROM memory have been invented [9, 6, 5].

The idea of POKs is based on the physical unclonable functions (PUFs) which rely on the IC's physical properties to generate random output from given input, and the output and input pairs consist of Challenge and Response Pairs (CRPs).

Hence, POKs could be considered a special type of PUF that only has one CRP, where the challenge is hardware fixed and the response is used as secret key. Differing from traditional method of storing secret keys as digital bits in non-volatile memory, it instantly generates a secret key depending on randomness of physical materials when given certain stimuli. This feature is effective in defeating physical tampering attacks such as micro-probing, laser cutting, and power analysis because these unauthorized access would inevitably modify the chip and sequentially destroy the secret.

E. Design of Light-weight Secure IoT Communication Protocols

6LoWPAN (IPv6 over Low-Power Wireless Personal Area Networks) [4] is the de-facto communication protocol for IoT devices. 6LoWPAN standard integrates IP-based infrastructure and IoT devices by specifying how IPv6 packets are routed in constrained networks such as IEEE 802.15.4 networks. 6LoWPAN itself does not provide enough security, and it is vulnerable to numerous attacks.

Due to the limited payload size of the link layer in 6LoWPAN networks, the 6LoWPAN standard defines fragmentation and reassembly of IPv6 packets. The 6LoWPAN adaptation layer is located between the network and the link layer. It provides header compression and packet fragmentation functionality for IPv6 packets, to enable the transmission of large IPv6 packets over size constrained link layer technologies such as IEEE 802.15.4. The data link of IEEE 802.15.4 with a frame length of maximum 127 bytes does not match the MTU (maximum transmission unit) of IPv6, which is 1280 bytes. 6LoWPAN provides fragmentation to over-sized IPv6 packets and reassembly of in-order or out-of-order fragments.

The attackers to the IoT devices using 6LoWPAN can be either an internal attacker or an external attacker. *Internal attackers* are those who participate in the 6LoWPAN network, and overhear, delay, alter, and drop legitimate packets. They can also send messages to other IoT devices within the network. For a protected network, the attacker must first extract the security keys from a legitimate IoT device to gain admission. *External attackers* are located outside the 6LoWPAN network and flood a specific resource constrained internal IoT device with numerous junk packets. If the packets are large, the fragmentation of these packets at the gateway may overload the gateway as well as the target IoT devices, considering the high volume of packets to be assembled and processed.

Based on the sending behaviors of an attacker, we propose effective security solutions to protect 6LoWPAN. In an IoT device, sensitive data should be saved in secured hardware systems (such as FPGA) and protected by appropriate cryptography. Encryption requirements for data at rest are covered by two categories: (1) unclassified systems require FIPS 140-2 encryption modules; and (2) classified systems require NSA/COMSEC-approved Type-1 encryption.

A public key authentication is added at the first fragment. The receiver device can identify the sender of the first fragment. A credit can be maintained for each IoT device. The historical

benign/malicious behaviors of a device can be recorded, so that during buffer resource competition, the credit score can be used to determine which one to discard. The credit score can be updated based on whether the decision is right or wrong. To avoid being exposed, the attacker device must send the complete IPv6 packet, so that the cost of launching attack is maximized (no longer just send a first fragment FRAG1).

A. Mitigating the Fragment Duplication Attack

To defend against fragment duplication attack, the work in [16] proposed a content-chaining scheme (Fig. 9) that binds the content of a fragmented packet to its FRAG1 instead of binding fragments to cryptographic sender identities. To this end, the legitimate sender adds an authentication token to each fragment during the 6LoWPAN fragmentation procedure. This allows the recipient to cryptographically verify the link between fragments at the time of reception and to discard maliciously duplicated fragments early on the forwarding path.

Fig 9: Content-chaining scheme

When generating a content chain, the legitimate sender device uses the payload of the last fragment as the seed value for the hash chain. It then appends the resulting content token to the previous fragment and computes the hash digest over the fragment content including the appended token. After iteratively performing this procedure over all packet fragments, the first fragment FRAG1 contains a token that commits to the overall packet content. Once the content chain construction has finished, the sender IoT device transmits each fragment with its respective content token.

When processing out-of-order fragments, a verifying IoT device follows a simple policy: (1) it only forwards fragments that have been verified successfully; (2) it stores out-of-order fragments without prior verification until all previous fragments have been received and verified.

B. Mitigating the Buffer Reservation Attack

The buffer reservation attack can be mitigated by enabling direct competition for the buffer resources between legitimate devices and an attacker. When buffer overload happens, the receiver device has to decide which packet to discard. The discard strategy is based on per-packet scores, capturing the extent to which a packet is completed along with the continuity in the sending behavior. In case of a buffer overload situation, the packet with the lowest score is discarded. The above solution has the following limitations:

(1) The target device can only be able to detect spoofed fragments after correctly receiving the first fragment FRAG1. The attacker can tamper the first fragment FRAG1 if it sits in

the forwarding path or it knows a faster forwarding path to the destination node (send a fake first fragment).

(2) The attacker may take advantage of the fact that out-of-order fragments cannot be validated immediately at a verifying node. It can send a first fragment FRAG1 with a large offset in order to occupy buffer resources, and block one of the previous fragments required for verification

(3) The proposed scheme is not compatible with token loss because a lost fragment invalidates the entire packet. The attacker can simply simulate the situation where a legitimate sender suffers packet loss to induce verification failure or buffer reservation.

To address the limitations, we propose the following solution. First, we consider the sending behaviors of an attacker, which are listed below:

(1) an attacker may send only the RST fragment and skip the remaining ones;

(2) an attacker may immediately send all but a few fragments;

(3) an attacker may stretch fragment transmission across the time span of the reassembly timeout.

Based on the sending behaviors of an attacker, we propose the following solution. A public key authentication is added at the first fragment. The receiver device can identify the sender of the first fragment FRAG1. A credit can be maintained for each IoT device. The historical benign/malicious behaviors of a device can be recorded, so that during buffer resource competition, the credit score can be used to determine which one to discard. The credit score can be updated based on whether the decision is right or wrong. To avoid being exposed, the attacker device must send the complete IPv6 packet, so that the cost of launching attack is maximized (no longer just send a first fragment FRAG1).

IV. CONCLUSION

The IoT also have many applications in commercial sectors, such as environmental monitoring, infrastructure management, smart buildings, and smart cities. This work has proposed and studied the development of novel and efficient security techniques that can protect IoT devices and enable secure communications over the Internet. Specifically, we have proposed (1) hardware based schemes for establishment of root of trust; (2) the design of a reliable and secure key generator and management system using SoC FPGA; (3) development of novel hardware-based secure authentication schemes for IoT devices; and (4) design of light-weight secure communication protocols for IoT devices.

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